

Studies on Surface Tension of Strontium Soaps in Aqueous 2-propanol at 35°

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The surface tension of strontium soaps in aqueous 2-propanol has been measured at 35° and the data have been discussed on the basis of Langmuir's approximate equation: $\gamma = \gamma_0(1 + X \ln Y) - X\gamma_0 \ln C$. Constants X and Y have been calculated for soap systems. Constant X is found to be independent of solvent composition in the mixture but it increases with increasing chain length of soaps. The values of Y show a marked change at 50% 2-propanol concentration which confirms that the change in nature of micelles takes place at about 50% 2-propanol concentration. The surface areas covered by 1 mol of the soaps have been evaluated.

SURFACE TENSION measurement has been used¹⁻⁵ for determining critical micelle concentration of surface active substances due to its accuracy for determining the inflection which is nearly the same for longer chain substances because surface tension changes over nearly the same magnitude. The values of CMC of calcium soaps in aqueous methanol are found⁶ to be independent of methanol concentration. The surface tension studies⁷⁻⁹ of barium soaps in aqueous 1-propanol have shown that the change in the nature of micelles from hydrophilic oleo micelle to lipophilic hydro micelle takes place at about 50% 1-propanol. Recently the conductance behaviour of strontium soaps in aqueous 2-propanol has indicated¹⁰ the presence of micelles in the solution and therefore, it appears desirable to measure the surface tension of these strontium soaps (Valerate, Caproate and Caprylate) solution to find out the surface behaviour and nature of micelles formed under different conditions.

Experimental

The chemicals were purified and the soaps were prepared by the methods described in the previous communication¹⁰. The surface tension of soap solutions was determined by stalagmometer in thermostatically controlled (35 ± 0.05°) bath. The densities were measured with a dilatometer calibrated with conductivity water. The accuracy of the results was checked by determining the surface tension of known solutions. The surface tension results are in dynes cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Surface tension, γ of soap solutions decreases with increasing soap concentration which is due to the decreasing effects in the surface energy of the solvent mixture. This indicates the surface active

behaviour of soaps. The plots (Fig. 1) of γ vs C show a sharp change at CMC¹⁰ which is independent of the solvent composition. Surface tension of soap solutions at first decreases rapidly upto 50%, then remains constant upto 60% and finally decreases

Fig. 1. Plots of surface tension vs concentration of strontium valerate in water 2-propanol mixture at 35°.

with increasing 2-propanol concentration. The plots (Fig. 2) of surface tension vs volume percent of 2-propanol show a change in the behaviour at 50% concentration which has also been observed earlier¹⁰.

Surface tension data have been interpreted using following equation

$$\gamma/\gamma_0 = 1 - KT \eta_s/\gamma_0 \ln(1 + \eta_s/K) \quad \dots (i)$$

where η_s is the number of exposed solvent sites per cm² of its surface, η_s is the concentration of the

Fig. 2. Plots of surface tension vs volume percent of 2-propanol at 35°.

×—0.004M strontium caprylate,
 ○—0.015M strontium caproate,
 Δ—0.010M strontium valerate.

substrate molecule cm^{-1} in bulk, K is a constant for solvent and other terms have their usual significance.

On substituting

$$KT \eta_s/\gamma_o = X \text{ and } \eta_s/K = C/Y \text{ one obtains}$$

$$\gamma/\gamma_o = 1 - K \ln (1 + C/Y) \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

where γ and γ_o are surface tensions of solutions of concentration C and pure solvent respectively. X and Y are constants. On applying the condition $C/Y \gg 1$, the following approximate expression which Langmuir showed to apply at high solute concentration and in condition of surface saturation was obtained.

$$\gamma = \gamma_o (1 + X \ln Y) - X \gamma_o \ln C \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

The plots (Fig. 3) of γ vs $\log C$ are linear which shows that the empirical equation (iii) is applicable to mixed systems also. The values of X and Y have been calculated from the linear plots and are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Constant X (Table 1) increases with increasing concentration of 2-propanol upto 60% in the solvent mixture and then decreases at higher concentrations. The values of X also increase with increasing chain length of soap. Since γ_o decreases with increasing

Fig. 3. Plots of surface tension vs log concentration of strontium valerate in water 2-propanol mixture at 35°.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF X FOR STRONTIUM SOAPS IN AQUEOUS 2-PROPANOL AT 35°C

Volume % of 2-Propanol	X.10 ²		
	Caprylate	Caproate	Valerate
10	3.254	2.847	2.542
20	3.635	3.115	2.855
30	3.658	3.419	3.263
40	3.736	3.566	3.388
50	3.793	3.618	3.441
60	3.821	3.801	3.473
70	3.776	3.587	3.398
80	—	3.473	3.067

TABLE 2—VALUES OF Y FOR STRONTIUM SOAPS IN AQUEOUS 2-PROPANOL AT 35°C

Volume % of 2-Propanol	Y.10 ³		
	Caprylate	Caproate	Valerate
10	0.543	0.782	3.041
20	2.759	3.617	9.376
30	2.460	3.032	6.934
40	2.382	2.773	4.132
50	1.991	2.601	2.339
60	1.514	2.310	3.162
70	1.580	4.833	6.223
80	—	4.949	6.982

concentration of 2-propanol in the water, the number of exposed solvent sites cm^{-2} should decrease for constant value of X. But the variation of values of X shows that number of exposed solvent sites cm^{-2} increase with increase in concentration of 2-propanol upto 60% and decreases at higher concentrations of alcohol. In other words, the concentration of soap molecules in the bulk increases with increase in content of 2-propanol and decreases at higher concentrations ($>60\%$). This occurs due

to change in the nature of micelles from hydrophilic oleo micelles to lipophilic hydromicelles in the soap solutions when the chain length of soap increases the number of exposed solvents sites cm^{-2} increases and therefore chance of micellization increases. This is also evident from the CMC values of strontium soaps, i.e., 0.015, 0.010 and 0.008 M respectively for valerate, caproate and caprylate.

The values of γ decrease with increasing volume percent of 2-propanol upto 50% and show an increase at higher concentration of alcohol. γ also decreases with increasing chain length of soaps.

Differentiating equation (iii)

$$d\gamma/d\ln C = -X\gamma_0 \quad \dots \text{(iv)}$$

On substituting this value in Gibb's adsorption equation the excess concentration of the solute per unit area of the surface Γ is found

$$\Gamma = -\frac{1}{RT} \cdot \frac{d\gamma}{d\ln C}$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{X\gamma_0}{RT} \quad \dots \text{(v)}$$

Hence the surface area, A covered by the soap micelle formed by 1 mole of the soap is

$$A = \frac{1}{\Gamma} = \frac{RT}{X\gamma_0} \quad \dots \text{(vi)}$$

The surface area, A occupied by the micelle formed by 1 mole of the soap has been calculated and is given in Table 3. It is observed that the surface area, A of soap micelles depends only on the surface tension of water-2-propanol mixture which decreases with the increase in the surface area. The increase in the size of the micelle occurs due to incorporation of alcohol in the micelle. It is observed that the surface area decreases with increase in chain length of soap.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF A FOR STRONTIUM SOAPS IN AQUEOUS 2-PROPANOL AT 35°C

Volume % of 2-Propanol	A.10 ⁻¹⁰ cm ²		
	Caprylate	Caproate	Valerate
10	1.845	2.118	2.961
20	2.107	2.490	2.658
30	2.508	2.683	2.810
40	2.683	2.810	2.951
50	2.744	2.880	3.026
60	2.683	2.683	2.951
70	2.973	3.107	3.269
80	—	3.258	3.690

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